

Impacts of Stator Current Angle and Rotor Current on Solid Losses of Hairpin Windings in Traction Electrically Excited Synchronous Machines

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Abstract— Hairpins in motor windings have attracted growing interest in the industrial community. However, the AC losses in the hairpins are much greater than those in the round wire when a high frequency current passes through, resulting in a reduction in the efficiency of the motor. Generally, AC losses are categorized into skin effect and proximity effect, which are caused by flux leakage. In this case, the magnetic leakage is due to the interaction of stator and rotor magnetic field variation, resulting in flux leakage at the slots opening. The synthesized magnetic field built by the stator current, including amplitude and angle, and the rotor current decides the level and position of stator iron-core saturation. Such saturation affects the flux leakage and furthermore hairpin AC losses. In this article, a model built in ANSYS to study the effect of current angles and rotor current on AC losses and AC resistance at different operation situations. The results of this paper can help improve the existing model of AC losses and therefore contribute to a more accurate motor control method.

Keywords—AC losses, Hairpin, Flux leakage, Current angle, Magnetic saturation

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently electric vehicles (EVs) have become the new alternative to fuel vehicles. The conventional internal combustion engine vehicles are mainly powered by non-renewable fossil fuels, which not only cause air pollution but also emit greenhouse gases. Compared to traditional fuel vehicles, electric vehicles (EVs) offer many advantages. They contribute to improving air quality by significantly reducing greenhouse gas emissions. EVs can also increase sustainability through integration with renewable energy sources. In addition, with fewer drive units, electric vehicles are quieter and have lower maintenance requirements [1]-[3].

Traction motor is a key component of EVs. The space for a traction motor in an EV is limited whereas the torque generated by the motor should be high enough to accelerate the vehicle. Therefore, a high torque density is crucial. To

achieve a desirable torque density, both high magnetic load and high electrical load need to be guaranteed.

To achieve high magnetic loads, permanent magnets are an alternative option. However, the geographical distribution of permanent magnets is limited, and the recycling efficiency is low. Without permanent magnets, electrically excited synchronous motors (EESMs) are considered more sustainable and are increasingly used as traction motors in EVs. The excitation system of EESMs enables dynamic adjustment of the field current, providing control over the field flux. Additionally, high power factor can be achieved using EESM due to the adjustable field current.

To achieve higher electrical loads, higher current densities are required. Increasing the slot fill factor of the stator is an effective option. Using hairpins is the most popular method of increasing slot filling factor. Compared with the round wire windings, hairpin windings have the following advantages [4]-[5]:

- a. High slot filling factor and high-torque density.
- b. Shorter end windings reduce costs and copper losses.
- c. Process steps can be controlled easily.

However, due to the large cross-sectional area of the hairpins, the AC losses due to the influence of magnetic leakage are significant. The flux leakage induces eddy currents within the hairpin, resulting in uneven current distribution, which leads to AC losses. In traction motors, flux leakage can have multiple sources. When passing AC current, each hairpin induces a magnetic field within itself. At the same time, the magnetic fields induced by hairpins in the same slot and by hairpins in neighbouring slots also affect each other. Magnetic field variations in EESMs are also due to changing magnetic fields formed by variable field currents delivered through the rotor windings. As well as the current angle of the stator affects the combined magnetic field of the stator and rotor fields, which in turn affects the magnetic field induced by the hairpin and the resulting AC losses.

A lot of studies have been done to explore the calculation of AC losses in hairpin and how to minimise AC losses. The shape of the hairpin and the size of the slots have been studied by many scholars. In [6], a 6-layer hairpin model is built and the AC losses factor for each layer of the hairpins are predicted using the analytical method. In [7], the effect of different layer numbers and aspect ratios on the AC loss of the hairpin is investigated using FEM. In addition to the number of layers, [8] analyses the effect of slot size and slot height on hairpin AC loss. In [9], an equivalent model of AC loss considering conductor gap for hairpin and round conductor windings is proposed and validated by FEM. Equivalent d-axis and q-axis circuits considering the AC resistance of the hairpins are proposed in [10], and AC losses are separated and calculated using frozen permeability. In [11], the AC copper losses of the hairpins are analysed by building a 3D model through FEM, and a shaped transposition winding is proposed to reduce the AC loss.

Hence, many studies have been presented on the analytical methods of AC losses in the hairpin as well as analysing the size and position of the slot in relation to the hairpin to make recommendations to reduce the AC losses [12]-[13]. However, there is few of studies investigating the relationship between the hairpins in EESMs being affected by flux leakage and the resulting AC losses. For EESM, the adjustable field flux makes the AC losses calculation even more complex. Accurate AC losses calculations can help EESMs to improve the design and help to select better operation points when calculating MTPA.

The aim of this research is to investigate the effect of the rotor magnetic field generated by the field current, stator current and the stator current angle on AC losses in EESM. To achieve this, firstly analyse the flux lines with different current angles using FEM. Secondly, analyse the AC losses and AC resistance in the hairpins under different currents and current angles. In the end, the effects of current angle and field current on the AC losses of the EESM are proved.

In section II, the reasons for the current angle and field current affecting the AC losses are introduced. In section III, the parameters of motor and the mesh in model are introduced. In section VI, by analysing the results under different operating conditions, the AC resistance is calculated. The effect of field current and current angle on AC resistance is verified by comparing the difference between AC resistance and DC resistance for different current angles.

II. AC LOSSES IN HAIRPIN

When DC current is flowing through the hairpin and the external magnetic field is static, the losses are called DC loss. When a hairpin is exposed to varying magnetic field, eddy currents will be induced which introduce an increase of copper losses. The copper losses in this condition are named AC losses. The varying magnetic field can be caused by the current flowing in the hairpin itself or other external sources.

A. Theory of AC losses

By neglecting the effect of the redistribution of eddy current on the magnetic field, the eddy current loss density in the conductor can be expressed as [14]

$$p_{eddy} = \frac{\omega^2 B^2 h w}{128 \rho_c} \quad (1)$$

In this equation, h represents the height of the cross section, w represents the width of the cross-section, ρ_c represents the resistivity of the conductor, B represents the magnitude of the magnetic field, and ω represents the angular frequency of the magnetic field.

B. Effect of current angle and field current in EESMs

The rotor magnetic field created by the field current and the stator magnetic field created by the stator current together form a synthetic magnetic field. This synthetic magnetic field passes through the stator core. The distribution of the flux in stator core will affect the distribution of flux leakage, which further influences the AC losses. The position of core saturation varies at different current angles, resulting in different amounts of AC losses.

In EESMs, the rotor field current is variable, causing it to affect the magnitude and location of the synthetic magnetic field. The stator current angle is the angle of the stator current to the d-axis, which also reflects the angle between the stator magnetic field and the rotor magnetic field.

Take a motor with 2 poles and 12 slots as a simple example as in Fig.1. The magnetic field formed by the stator current is combined with the rotor field to form a flux linkage Φ . When this synthetic flux linkage of the d-axis and the q-axis points to a certain position in the stator, the core may be saturated at that position. The additional flux in the form of leakage affects the hairpins in the neighbouring slots, inducing eddy currents inside these hairpins and generating AC losses.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the current and magnetic chain of a 2/12 motor at a moment in time

The different saturation positions are at various distances from the slots, causing eddy currents in the hairpins close to the slot openings, which ultimately show a correlation between the current angle and the AC losses.

For example, when there are 2 slots per pole per phase, the magnetic circuit is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Schematic diagram of the magnetic circuit under one pole

In Fig. 2, the magneto motive force (MMF) in stator yoke can be expressed as

$$F_i = \sum_{n=1}^{N_{layer}} i_n / N_{paralle} \quad (2)$$

Where i_n is the current passing through the n th layer of hairpin. N_{layer} is the number of layers in each slot.

Since the three-phase currents passing through each slot are different, the MMF at the yoke corresponding to each slot can be expressed as

$$F_n = n_a i_a + n_b i_b + n_c i_c \quad (3)$$

Where n_a , n_b and n_c are the number of hairpins in one slot passing i_a , i_b and i_c . And they conform to the following equation as

$$\begin{cases} n_a n_b n_c = 0 \\ n_a + n_b + n_c = N_{layer} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

In formula (3), i_a , i_b and i_c can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} i_a = I_d \cos(\omega t) - I_q \sin(\omega t) \\ i_b = I_d \cos(\omega t - \frac{2}{3}\pi) - I_q \sin(\omega t - \frac{2}{3}\pi) \\ i_c = I_d \cos(\omega t + \frac{2}{3}\pi) - I_q \sin(\omega t + \frac{2}{3}\pi) \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Where I_d and I_q can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} I_d = I_m \cos(\theta_i) \\ I_q = I_m \sin(\theta_i) \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Where I_m is the amplitude of stator current and θ_i is the current angle.

From (2) ~ (6), the MMF of each slot is related to current amplitude and angle. For a short pitch winding, the MMF of each slot in Fig. 2 can be expressed as

$$\begin{cases} F_1 = 2i_c \\ F_2 = i_a + i_c \\ F_3 = 2i_a \\ F_4 = i_a + i_b \\ F_5 = 2i_b \\ F_6 = i_b + i_c \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

The amplitude of MMF in each slot is shown as Fig. 3. Since there are six slots corresponding to each pole, the MMF

of stator core under each pole varies with the current angle in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3. The MMF of each slot

At current angles of 0° , 45° and 90° , the flux linkage of one pole is shown in Fig. 4. When the current angle is 0° , the flux mainly passes through the stator teeth, and the reluctance in the magnetic circuit is small. When the current angle is 45° , the flux offset towards the q-axis, and a part of the flux goes through the hairpins in the slots. Being affected by current angle, the flux needs to flow in the tangential direction. The tangential reluctance in the air gap and the one in the stator slots are similar. Hence a significant portion of flux choose to flow in the slots, which induces eddy currents and AC losses. When the current angle is 90° , the flux goes through the stator teeth in the direction of the q-axis. At this time the flux going through the slots is affected by the current angle and passes through the hairpins in parallel. Since there is mainly the stator teeth reluctance and hairpins reluctance, the total reluctance in the magnetic circuit is less than at 45° and larger than at 0° .

(a) Flux of 0 deg. current angle under one pole

(b) Flux of 45 deg. current angle under one pole

(c) Flux of 90 deg. current angle under one pole

Fig. 4. Flux in magnetic circuit at different current angles

III. SIMULATION MODEL

A. 2D model and parameters of motor

To analyse the variation of AC losses with current angles and currents, a 2D model of EESM is established in ANSYS, as shown in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. 2D model of motor in ANSYS

The stator of motor is similar with other motors using hairpin. In each slot, there are 8 layers hairpin. Other parameters of the motor are shown in table I.

TABLE I. PARAMETERS OF EESM

Parameters	Value
Number of poles	8
Number of slots	48

Parameters	Value
Airgap length	0.75mm
Active length	148mm
Stator current	600A
Rotor current	5A
Maximum power	300kW
Maximum torque	460Nm
Maximum speed	1800rpm

The cross section of the hairpin used in this motor is shown in Fig.5. The active part of DC resistance of hairpin is calculated as 3.1mΩ.

Fig. 6. Cross section of hairpin

B. Element size of hairpin meshing

Since with each layers at different distances from the slot opening, the mesh size should not be the same for every hairpin. In order to get more accurate AC losses results, it is necessary to make the mesh size of the hairpin smaller than the skin depth. When the rotor rotating speed is 18000rpm, the frequency is 1200Hz. The skin depth can be calculated by formula

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sigma \pi \mu_0 \mu_r f}} \quad (2)$$

where δ is the skin depth, σ is the conductivity of copper, μ_0 is air permeability, μ_r is the relative permeability of copper, f is the frequency.

The result of hairpin skin depth after calculation is 1.882mm. The closer the hairpin is to the slot the more slot harmonics it is exposed to and the less skin depth it has. For an 8-layer hairpin winding, the first two layers are more affected to slot harmonics, especially the first layer. Therefore, the mesh of the first two layers should not exceed 1.882 mm. In order to reduce the number of mesh elements and simplify the simulation, the hairpin mesh size is finally set as in Table II. The motor after meshing is shown in Fig. 7.

TABLE II. MESH SIZE OF EACH LAYER HAIRPIN

Layers of hairpin	Element size/mm
1 st ~2 nd layer	0.5
3 rd ~8 th layers	2

Fig. 7. Mesh plot of different hairpin layers

IV. RESULTS OF CURRENT ANGLE AND FIELD CURRENT

Based on the motor model above, considering the current angle and field current as the two affecting factors, the AC losses of total and each layer of hairpin are analysed as follows. Since the AC losses at the same current but different speeds are identical in shape, only the AC losses at 6000 rpm are presented and compared in this section, which is the base speed of this motor.

A. Effect on total AC losses

With the maximum stator current, the flux lines at 0°, 45° and 90° are shown in Fig. 8 for different field currents. When field current is 0, the direction of the flux lines at different current angles is consistent with the analysis in Fig. 4. When there is a field current, the flux in the d-axis direction is strengthened, causing the total flux to be shifted towards the d-axis direction, which is obvious in Fig. 8(c).

(a) Flux lines and AC losses of 0 deg. current angle for field current of 0A and 5A

(b) Flux lines and AC losses of 45 deg. current angle for field current of 0A and 5A

(c) Flux lines and AC losses of 90 deg. current angle for field current of 0A and 5A

Fig. 8. AC losses at different field currents at current angle of 0 deg., 45deg. and 90 deg.

From Chapter 2.2, saturation of the stator is related to the total flux. In this motor, the total flux comes from stator current and field current. Fig. 9 shows the AC losses when the stator and rotor currents apply separately. Since the AC losses when only field currents is applied are small and constant regardless of the current angle, as the results shown in Fig. 9(b).

(a) Stator current only

(b) Field current only

Fig. 9. AC losses at stator and field currents separate of 6000rpm

It is shown in Fig. 9 (a) that the AC losses are more current angle dependent when the stator current increases. This is due to the fact that, when the stator core is saturated, the core reluctance increases and then, the leakage flux increases.

Fig. 10 shows the AC losses when the stator current and field current operate simultaneously. From Fig. 10 (a), when stator current is relatively small, AC losses reduces with field current at 180 deg compared to no field current. It is because the flux produced by field current at 180 deg in d-axis counteracts stator magnetic flux and eases core saturation.

When stator current is 400A in Fig. 10 (b), AC losses show the similar tendency with Fig. 10 (a) at 5A field current. When field current is less than 5A, AC losses are dependent on current angle. This is because the rotor flux produced by field current at 180° is not high enough to ease the core saturation.

In Fig. 10 (c), when the stator current is 600A, the AC losses vary with current angle regardless of the existence of field current. This is because the core is deeply saturated at this stator current. And flux produced by field current of 5A is too low to alleviate core saturation. Thus, the AC losses are dependent on current angle

(a) AC losses for different field currents with 200A stator current

(b) AC losses for different field currents with 400A stator current

(c) AC losses for different field currents with 600A stator current

Fig. 10. AC losses at different filed currents of 6000rpm

Based on the AC losses results, AC resistance can be calculated as shown in Fig.11.

(a) If = 0A (b) If = 1A (c) If = 3A (d) If = 5A

Fig. 11. AC resistance at different currents and current angles

From Figs. 10 and 11, the AC losses and AC resistance reach maximum values close to the current angle of 45° and decrease as the angle approaches 180°, regardless of field current. Comparing the AC resistance with the DC resistance, as shown in Fig. 12. As can be seen in Fig. 12, the tendency of AC resistance is similar to AC losses at the same stator current.

Fig. 12. AC resistance of different filed currents and stator currents with current angle 45deg. and 180deg.

V. CONCLUSION

In this study, the correlation between saturation of stator core and AC losses has been analysed. The magnetic saturation of core is affected by synthesized flux, which is built by stator current and field current, and current angle. The saturation of core leads to different magnetic leakage from the slots, and ultimately results in the AC losses of the hairpin being affected. This concept is verified by establishing an EESM model through the FEM and analysing the AC losses and AC resistance at different stator currents, field currents and current angles. It is proved that when the stator current is large, the stator core is saturated and the AC losses show a correlation with the current angle. The higher the saturation extent, the higher the AC losses. The rotor magnetic field also affects the saturation level of the stator core through the current angle, thereby affecting the AC losses. This paper helps the further accuracy of the model of hairpin during the motor design process.

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